

Determination of Sulfides and Disulfides with Phenyliodoacetate

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A titrimetric procedure is described for determining organic disulfides and sulfides by oxidation with phenyliodoacetate in dilute acetic acid. By applying a second method, sulfides and disulfides can be determined in presence of each other. Mercaptans, if present, can also be determined. The procedure is precise to about $\pm 0.4\%$.

ORGANIC disulfides have been determined by Kolthoff¹ by reduction to the corresponding mercaptans and amperometric titration of the mercaptans with silver nitrate. This method has the disadvantage of relatively low precision and accuracy of the reduction method. The procedure of Siggia and Edsberg² yields reliable results and has been widely used. But, when the samples are colored (especially the crude materials), the end point is indistinct since it is taken as the appearance of the first permanent bromine coloration. Mercaptans, if present in large amounts, vitiate the results as the bromine oxidation of mercaptans is somewhat non-stoichiometric.

As a procedure of wider applicability, a new oxidation method has been devised. The present method involves oxidation of the disulfide with phenyliodoacetate in dilute acetic acid; α -disulfone probably being the reaction product.

Samples were treated with an excess of iodoacetate in 30 to 80% acetic acid medium. The residual oxidant was determined by adding a measured excess of ascorbic acid (which reacts in a molar ratio of 1 : 1 with iodoacetate) followed by a back titration with standard iodine.

The same procedure is applicable to the determination of organic sulfides. The reaction is the oxidation of sulfide to the sulfoxide.

In both cases, as high as four fold excess of the oxidant used, does not cause high results during the period specified.

Mixtures of sulfides and disulfides can be determined by first determining a total of them by oxidation with iodoacetate. Then, by using the method of Kolthoff¹, the disulfide alone can be determined; the sulfide is then obtained by difference. Error is introduced in this method by the low accuracy in

reduction procedure and by the fact that the final result depends on a subtraction and that the disulfide oxidation involves 4 moles of iodoacetate while the sulfide oxidation involves 1 mole. Best results are obtained with samples low in disulfide and high in sulfide; here, the error from the disulfide results, does not figure too prominently in the final results.

Mercaptans are also oxidized quantitatively by phenyliodoacetate, and act as interferences if they are not determined separately and the results corrected for their presence.

This procedure has been used for determining mercaptans³ in presence of sulfides and disulfides and was found to afford excellent results. The procedure for determining mercaptans, involved the titration of sample, dissolved in glacial acetic acid (diluted with water at the time of titration), with a standard phenyliodoacetate solution in the presence of starch-iodide; the end point was shown by blue color of starch-iodine.

Samples of sulfide or disulfide containing mercaptans are determined by first evaluating the mercaptans by the procedure described, then an identical sample is titrated with iodoacetate to the first ascertained titer in the absence of any starch-iodide to convert mercaptan to the disulfide; the total sulfide and disulfide is finally determined. The amount of disulfide produced by the oxidation of mercaptan is subtracted to get sulfide or disulfide originally present. With samples, having higher ratios of mercaptan to disulfide or sulfide, the results were unaffected.

Experimental

Reagents :

Phenyliodoacetate (0.05M) was prepared in anhydrous acetic acid by the method of Pausacker⁴; it was standardized iodometrically. Sulfides and

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disulfides were of high purity available and as a check, were determined by the method of Siggia and Edsberg² and by total sulfur analysis (Tables 1 & 2). Crude samples of sulfides and disulfides were prepared⁵ in this laboratory and their purity was determined by total sulfur analysis (Table 3). Mercaptan

out. The flask was left on bench for at least 20 min. (40 min. in the case of methionine). A measured excess of 0.05M ascorbic acid solution was added and the contents swirled well. The remaining ascorbic acid was back titrated with 0.05N iodine. A blank determination was also carried out.

TABLE 1. DETERMINATION OF SULFIDES

Sample	Purity (%)	
	Present method	Comparison Method
Dibenzyl sulfide	98.8	99.2 Total sulfur analysis
Dibutyl sulfide	99.7	99.4 Bromimetric
Methylpropyl sulfide	95.3	96.0 Bromimetric
Methionine	99.6	100.2 Total sulfur analysis

TABLE 2. DETERMINATION OF DISULFIDES

Sample	Purity (%)	
	Present method	Bromimetric titration
Dibutyl disulfide	97.2	96.9
Dibenzyl disulfide	99.7	100.1
Dipentyl disulfide	98.3	98.0
Dipropyl disulfide	94.6	94.5
Cystine	99.0	99.3
Diphenyl disulfide	95.4	95.8

TABLE 3. DETERMINATION OF CRUDE SAMPLES

Sample	Purity (%)	
	Present method	Total sulfur analysis
Dibenzyl disulfide	84.2	84.8
Dibutyl sulfide	79.5	81.0
Dibenzyl sulfide	87.5	88.2

samples were purified before use, and their purity was determined iodimetrically⁶. All other chemicals were of reagent grade.

General Procedure for the Determination of Sulfide or Disulfide :

A sample containing about 1 to 2 m mole of sulfide or about 0.2 to 0.8 m mole of disulfide was weighed into a 250 ml. Erlenmeyer flask and dissolved in 15 ml of glacial acetic acid. A solution of phenyl-iodoacetate was added, about 50% in excess. Calculated volumes of distilled water were added so as to adjust acid concentration between 30 to 80% by volume. (Reactions were very slow in anhydrous acetic acid and catalyzed moderately by water). Less water was used when the sample precipitates

Results and Discussion

Quantitative results for the analysis of pure as well as crude samples of sulfide and disulfide are given in Tables 1 to 3. In Table 4, results are

TABLE 4. DETERMINATION OF DISULFIDES FORMED IN COMPLETELY TITRATED MERCAPTAN SOLUTION

RSH	m mole		RSSR, recovery (%)
	RSH titrated	RSSR found	
Mercaptoacetic acid	0.581	0.288	99.2
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	1.163	0.578	99.4
Toluene- α -thiol	0.874	0.431	98.5
Benzenethiol	1.028	0.520	101.0
1-Butanethiol	0.759	0.380	100.3
1-Pentanethiol	0.287	0.142	99.3

given for the determination of disulfide formed by titration of mercaptan solution by iodoacetate.

The present method of determining sulfides and disulfides is accurate and precise, and requires no special care, since the final determination involves the familiar ascorbic acid-iodine titration. The residual phenyl-iodoacetate can also be determined iodometrically; however, the present modification is a less expensive one. Because of the non-reactivity of iodoacetate with dextrose and most of the amino acids, under the conditions used for determination, the present method appears to process unique value.

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